

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Heat Sensitive Magic: Unveiling Thermochromic Substances in Pharmacy

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 30 Sept. 2025

Keywords:

Thermochromic materials,
temperature sensitivity,
chromogenic materials,
Leucodyes, Pharmaceutical
applications

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17231463

ABSTRACT

Thermochromic substances are materials that change its colour when there is change in external stimuli like temperature or excessive heat¹, this unique property can be used for transport and packaging of pharmaceuticals². Thermochromic substances are type of chromogenic materials¹, This system can be used for temperature sensitive drugs and pharmaceutical materials that need suitable environmental conditions for storage and transport⁶. In pharmaceutical market use of this materials are increasing as it can be cost effective to use and easily detectable, this review focuses on Introduction of Thermochromic substances its system, pharmaceutical growth of this substances, Applications in various field, future trends and challenges in pharmaceuticals market¹⁴.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Chromogenic Materials:

Chromogenic materials are the materials that undergo changes in their molecular structure,

appearance, colour, bonding as well as optical activities when external stimuli apply to them¹

They classified based on their response to external stimuli:

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig:1.1) Types of Thermochromic Substances.

- Photochromic materials: These are the materials having different absorption spectra when they are exposed to light they undergo reversible transformation ²
- Thermochromic materials: These are the substances that show changes in colours when there are fluctuations in temperature ¹
- Electrochromic materials: These are the materials that give reversible opacity or colour change in response to any electrical stimulus ³
- Solvatochromic materials: These are the materials that change their colour when there is a change in the polarity of the solvent ¹
- Halochromic materials: These materials undergo a change in colour when there is the presence of gas or vapour ²
- Humid chromic materials: When there is a change in the humidity, these materials undergo a colour change ¹
- Carsolchromic materials: These materials change their colour in the presence of an electrical beam of light and shift to different colours ²
- Piezo chromic materials: These are the materials that are generally in the solid phase but when there are external stimuli they will change their colour and undergo compression ¹

1..2Thermochromic substances:

Thermochromic materials response to fluctuations in temperature they change there colour in response to change in temperature, they also known as temperature sensitive pigments or Thermochromic pigments. The phenomenon

shown by Thermochromic materials also known as "Thermochromism"⁴.

The Thermochromic system is either direct Thermochromism or indirect Thermochromism based system:

This is the basic principle of Thermochromic materials they respond to fluctuations in temperature and structural change can be seen in these materials ⁷ When there is negative temperature the structural shape of molecule will contract and after the contract, they will show

different colour e.g. Blue ⁵ When there is positive temperature the structure of the molecule will expand and after the structural change, they will show different colour e.g. Red ⁵

1.4Types of Thermochromic substances:

- Leucodyed based Thermochromic materials:- This materials use the leuco dyes they respond to temperature shift and change there colour examples can be , ex. Leucodyed based , thermochromic ink³
- Cholesteric liquid crystal based thermochromic substances:- This cholesteric liquid changes it's colour when there is change in the temperature ^{7 19}
- Thermochromic pigments:- This are the pigments that have it's own mechanism and changes it's colour when there is fluctuations in temperature ⁸
- Microencapsulated thermochromic materials:- This materials uses microcapsule to encapsulated thermochromic pigments or Leucocyte ⁹
- Polymer -based thermochromic materials:- This materials uses the polymer matrix to encapsulated thermochromic pigments ⁶
- Ceramic-based thermochromic materials:- This materials use the ceramic matrix to encapsulated thermochromic pigments or leucon dyes ²⁰
- Nanoparticle -based thermochromic materials:- these materials use nanoparticles to produce a colour changes in response to temperature change ¹³
- Shape memory alloy bases thermochromic materials:- This materials use shape memory alloy to produce colour change in response to temperature changes ²¹

- Electrochromic thermochromic materials:- This materials used to detect the temperature change by using electric current ²²
- Photochromic thermochromic materials:- This materials can be used as thermochromic materials in some cases as they change it's colour in response to light ¹⁶

1.5 Interlink between thermochromic substances and pharmaceutical applications:

The use of Thermochromic materials in pharmacy dates back to 1970s, when first thermochromic pigments were developed, Thermochromic substances and it's relation with pharmaceutical products it's fascinating connection . ¹

Thermochromic substances change its colour in response to change in the temperature change and this property is being leveraged in various applications of this substances in pharmaceutical industry ⁶

2. Market size

The market size of thermodynamic materials in pharmaceutical industry has been growing since 2010. According to report by marketstandmarkets, global thermochromic materials market size was valued at \$1.3 billion in 2010 and is expected to reach \$ 3.4 billion by 2025, the market size of ¹⁴ Thermochromic materials in pharmaceutical industry has grown by \$ 1.35 billion representing a compound annual growth rate of 14.1 %⁵.

Fig 2.1) Market Size Growth.

3. Application of Thermochromic materials in pharmaceutical products

Thermochromic materials in pharmacy have wide range of applications, in recent advance technologies thermochromic materials use in analysing of pharmaceutical products

3.1 Thermochromic materials in temperature sensitive packaging :

Form the 1960 the temperature sensitive packaging is used for pharmaceutical industry first in 1960 the researcher start to use this materials in packaging ¹⁸

- First commercial use of thermochromic materials in pharmacy:

First commercial use of thermochromic materials in pharmaceutical industry was in 1990 when company, colorchange, introduced a temperature sensitive packaging systems for use in pharmaceutical industry. ⁴This system known as “colour change temperature indicator ”, used as thermochromic material to change colour in response to temperature changes, indicating whenever pharmaceutical product had been exposed to excessive heat or cold it is very important to analyze that pharmaceutical products, importantly parentals are being in right temperature for storage¹⁰.

3.2 Types of thermochromic materials in packaging:

Thermochromic materials in packaging can be varies by types for they use.

- **Thermochromic materials in packaging of food:**

This are the materials that can be used to indicate that food in packaging is safe for intake or it expired, It is used in most of the packaging food. The thermochromic materials on labels change it colour indicating the expiry of food ¹¹.

- **Thermochromic materials in pharmaceutical package:**

It uses is growing across the world as it is consider safe to use for packaging, in pharmaceutical industry the pharmaceutical products are directly related to patient safety so it consider as safe for pharmaceuticals so it use as a indicator for packaging like tablet's, paediatric pharmaceutical products etc., Temperature is key factor that need to determine for storage as right temperature

essential for potency and efficiency of pharmaceutical products^{6 18}

3.3 Thermochromic labels:

This can indicate if pharmaceutical products expose to heat or cold, it provides a visual indication. And this labels are made from Leucodyes or liquid crystals that alter the molecular structure when exposed to different temperatures⁷, this labels mainly use when vaccine, injections, insulin and antibiotics are stored and transported at correct temperature, Leucodyes are organic carbon based chemical and thermochromic ink.¹⁰ Thermochromic labels give easy – to – see guarantee that product is safe to use they activated in both heat activated and cold activated versions.¹²

4. FUTURE TRENDS IN THERMOCHROMIC SUBSTANCES

Thermochromic materials hold immense growth potential to evaluate temperature monitoring in pharmaceutical industry, when currently this materials are use in packaging and transport future applications and research can expand this use into more advanced and integrated systems, some can be:

4.1 Enhanced Shelf life and stability –

Uv-light sensitive thermochromic pigments that can be highly resistance to UV light, humidity and chemical resistance ¹⁷

4.2 Eco friendly and Biodegradable system –

To develop non – toxic Thermochromic agents like (anthocyanin's, curcumin) and to reduce environmental impacts ^{11 23}

4.3 Smart sensors development –

Combination of thermochromic indicators with RFID, NFC, or IoT-based devices to create hybrid smart packaging that can be capable of recording, storing, and transmitting temperature data.²⁴

4.4 Broader Pharmaceutical Applications –

Applying thermochromic coatings directly to dosage forms such as tablets, syrups, or injectable vials to provide real-time patient-level assurance of product safety.²⁵

4.5 Personalized Medicine and Patient Compliance –

Using colour-change indicators in patient-specific kits to help and alert users about improper storage or missed doses, improving treatment outcomes.²⁶

4.6 Regulatory Standardization –

Establishing global guidelines for the use of thermochromic materials in pharmaceutical packaging to ensure safety, accuracy, and reliability across markets.^{27 28.}

4.7 Cost-Effective Manufacturing –

Scaling up low-cost production methods, including roll-to-roll printing and microencapsulation techniques, to make thermochromic systems accessible for mass use in developing nations.³⁰

5. CHALLENGES:

5.1 Overcoming stability and scalability issues:

- **Stability** – Many organic thermochromic pigments, particularly leuco dyes, are prone to UV degradation, humidity sensitivity, and chemical interference. This can lead to faded or inaccurate colour responses over time. Solutions include microencapsulation, UV-protective coatings, and the development of

inorganic or hybrid pigments with higher thermal and photo stability.^{3 9 17.}

- **Scalability** – Large-scale production faces hurdles such as high encapsulation costs, maintaining uniform pigment performance, and integrating thermochromic systems into existing packaging lines without affecting product integrity. Advances in roll-to-roll printing, low-cost polymer carriers, and automated quality control systems are key to making thermochromic technology more affordable and accessible.^{27 28 29.}

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HOW TO CITE: Amruta Patwardhan*, Pooja Karpe, Dr. Sachidanand Angdi, Heat Sensitive Magic: Unveiling Thermochromic Substances in Pharmacy, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 9, 3594-3608 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231463>

